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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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The Unexplained Known

At the course of time, an academic semester will end,
Let it be not too late to mend.
In the midst of uncertainties
Series of assessment results are about to be told...

On top of this medical-surgical nursing subject,
Never should it be taken for granted.
Recall on previous lessons is demanded,
Access to resources is unlimited.

Youthful demands are set aside,
Mindset and focus are prioritized.
Understanding is essential,
Nurturing each potential.

Drastic change on study habits is felt,
Sometimes reading is loved instead of hate.
As always, the teacher tries to consider,
Notwithstanding the complacency of the learners.

In the context of disease process and nursing care,
Everything is a lot to bear.
Let the question be asked, what comes next?
Reassuring self all will be at peace.

Now a teacher can only hope...
Many students will make it through...
As this subject will make a mark,
Never will it be again, an unexplained known...